

EVALUATION OF EFFICIENCY AND RELIABILITY OF TECHNICAL OPERATION OF VEHICLES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6382804>

Akhmedov Alisher Parda oglu

MAX-1 group students.¹

Raimov Saydullo Khamidullayevch

MAX-1 group students.¹

Rahmonkulov Fyasix Khamzaevich

Scientific adviser -.¹

¹Tashkent State Transport University

Annotation: *This article describes the state of technical operation of automobiles, ie the technology of maintenance and repair of automobiles, technological equipment used in the production of motor transport enterprises, the organization of logistics and resource saving methods, Exploitation of road transport in various extreme climatic and road conditions, in isolation from the main production bases and specialized rolling stock, the directions of the harmful effects of road transport on the environment and ways to reduce them.*

Keywords: *motion, factor, control, wheel, property, dynamics, traction, engine, capital, oil, repair, compression.*

Introduction. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev noted, during the years of independence our country has undergone great changes in all spheres, Uzbekistan has found its rightful place in the world community, is making great strides in all areas. Undoubtedly, one of the great opportunities provided by independence is the establishment of the automotive industry in our country. Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most influential countries in the world in the development of the automotive industry. This is due to the fact that a number of modern car companies have been set up in the country in cooperation with foreign companies to produce various types of cars. In addition, in the future, Uzbekistan intends to create a system of rolling stock that will have its own brand and will be able to compete with foreign car brands in a positive way. At the same time, the movement structure of the national economy and personal use, after a certain distance, to increase the efficiency of their maintenance and current repair process, to improve

their operational and economic performance. Keeping pace is also one of the most important tasks facing motorists.

Road transport has a special place in the general transport system. It accounts for up to 80% of all tons of cargo transported in the country by all modes of transport. The great role and importance of road transport in the transport system of the national economy is due to the large labor and material costs, both in the field of transportation and maintenance and repair of rolling stock. About 9 million people, or more than 60% of all transportation workers, work in road transport. However, the total cost of maintaining this type of transport is about 60% of all transportation costs.

To ensure the operation of road transport rolling stock, reliability in transportation, there is a need to create specialized enterprises for the storage, maintenance, repair and maintenance of vehicles. Such enterprises constitute the total fixed assets of road transport, the efficient use of which is the main task of every road transport enterprise (ATP). That is why today the demand for technical maintenance of cars is growing.

The main part. Dependence of traffic safety on operational characteristics Traffic safety depends on operational characteristics of the car, such as stability, maneuverability, ability to rotate in a small area. It is known that the steered wheels lose their neutral position under the influence of accidental impulses on the road, even during linear motion. A car with unstable steering wheels cannot move stably. It will change direction and the driver will have to constantly turn the steering wheel. If the wheels are not stable, the driver's work will be difficult, there is a risk of the car overturning, which in turn will worsen its stability, increase the wear of the tire and steering gear parts. The stability of the steered wheels is also necessary when turning the car. Returning the wheels to their original position at the end of the turn makes the driver's job easier and reduces the chances of the car colliding with an obstacle. Good handling also depends in many ways on the balance of the wheels. If the car is moving at high speed, the wheels will spin and it will be difficult to drive. About 15% of traffic accidents are caused by overturning a car. Rapid turning of the steering wheel, incorrect placement of the load on the body, slipping of the wheels, etc. causes the car to overturn. A decrease in the force of the wheel on the road causes the car to overtake. It is especially dangerous to push the rear wheels to the side. It is not possible to brake or increase the speed of the car at this time, as it may increase overturning and overturning.

Influence of operational factors on road safety

Many operational factors affect the road safety through its operational characteristics. First of all, the driver must know the forces acting on him during the movement, the value and direction of which change during their turning and braking. If these forces are not taken into account and the turn is made at high speed, the car may overturn. The high center of gravity of the car has a negative impact on traffic safety. If a large load is placed on the truck, the height of the car's center of gravity will increase, which will increase the risk of the car overturning. The coefficient of road tires of car wheels also affects traffic safety. The value of the gear ratio depends on how much the tire tread is worn. If the tread is over-worn (especially on a wet road), the bite rate will decrease and the car will slip on the side and lose its stability. The unsteady movement of the car violates the traffic safety of the road. The technical condition of the car's braking system is a key factor in ensuring safety. Before driving, the driver must check that each wheel is evenly adjusted and that the brakes are working properly. Uneven adjustment of the braking mechanism on the wheels leads to a variety of braking forces. At the same time, if the car brakes, it slides to the side and loses its stability. Occasionally, improper installation of a hose in a pneumatic or hydraulically driven brake system can cause a sudden break. As a result, the brakes do not work and traffic safety is compromised.

The stability of the steered wheels depends on the transverse and longitudinal tilt angles of the drill, the lateral tilt angle of the wheel, the approach of the wheels. The driver must keep the car wheels in good condition by systematically adjusting the misalignment of the wheels. This is one of the main factors in ensuring traffic safety. In addition, the balance of the car's wheels (especially passenger cars) has a positive effect on its handling, and therefore on traffic safety. The psychological and physiological condition of the driver can also affect traffic safety. In order to drive a car well, the driver must have sharp eyesight, be able to distinguish colors, and remain alert even when the road conditions change.

Influence of operating factors on traction dynamics The dynamic parameters of a car, determined theoretically or experimentally, are suitable for its movement in certain conditions. For example, if the road is straight and smooth, its total resistance Σ does not change, there are no obstacles in the movement. The calculated dynamic performance of the car determines its maximum capabilities. Dynamic index determined by calculation of the car and experimentally chlari are quite different from each other. This is due to changes in the technical condition and operating conditions of the car. The technical condition of the car is understood as its

readiness to perform transport work, ie compliance of the mechanism, unit and devices with the norms specified in the rules of technical operation. When the car is operated for a long time, wear and tear of parts, changes in the tone, etc. will worsen its technical condition, as a result of which the operational characteristics of the car will change.

Spread of piston group details, failure to install gypsum in place of valves, incorrect fuel combustion time, etc. causes a decrease in engine power. For example, if the ignition time is delayed, the engine power will be significantly reduced. If the ignition timing is too advanced, the engine will start detonating. Changes in engine power worsen the car's traction dynamics. During operation, the technical condition of the car chassis deteriorates, and the wording of the mechanisms quickly deteriorates. For example, if the main drive bearings are tightened, or if the bearing gears are misaligned, the energy required to overcome the friction in the transmission will be large, and the car's dynamics will deteriorate. If the approach of the brakes or front wheels is incorrectly adjusted, the dynamic performance will decrease. As the car's dynamics deteriorate, its meticulous running time, maximum speed, and acceleration are reduced.

The maximum speed of the overhauled car is reduced by 10-12%: the time spent on acceleration to reach the maximum speed is 25-30% longer than in a new car. Deterioration of the performance of the car is caused by the use of poor quality fuel and oil. In engines with a high compression ratio, detonation occurs when small amounts of gasoline are used, which reduces engine power. If gasoline is stored for a long time, resins will form in it, which will reduce the surface area of the inlet pipe by forming a solid layer. As a result, the uniform distribution of the combustible mixture in the cylinders deteriorates, engine power is reduced by 15-20%. Engine power varies depending on the operating conditions of the vehicle. When the car is operated in cold conditions, the preparation of the combustible mixture and its combustion conditions change, and the transfer of heat to the atmosphere increases. If the car is operated in hot climates, the engine will overheat, the filling of the cylinders with air will deteriorate due to the thinness of the air, steam bubbles will form in the fuel system and pipes. These factors reduce the effective power of the engine, resulting in deteriorating vehicle dynamics. Advantages in the design of the car can have a positive effect on the traction dynamics only if it is in good technical condition. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out timely technical inspection of units and components of the car.

REFERENCES:

1. Avtomobillar. konstruksiyaasoslari. Muxitdinov A.A. vaboshq. – T. «Istiqlolnuri», 2016.
2. Transport vositalariningtuzilishi (Design of vehicles). Muxitdinov A.A., Sattivaldiev B., XakimovSh.K. – T. “Ta’limnashriyoti”, 2014.
3. Qodirov S.M. vaQodirxonov M.O. Dvigatelvaavtomobillarnazariyasi. Toshkent , «O`qituvchi», 1981 y.
4. Mamatov X.M. vaboshqalar. Avtomobillar. .Toshkent , «O`qituvchi», 1982 y.
5. Qodirxonov M.O., Rasulov G.G. Avtomobilnazariyasidanmasalalarto`plami. .Toshkent , «O`qituvchi», 1996 y.
6. ЛатиповаА.С., ФаробинЯ.Э. Автомобил. Теория эксплуатационных свойств. Москва, «Машиностроение», 1989 г.
7. X.M.Mamatov. Avtomobillar. (Avtomobillarkonstruksiyasidanprogrammallashtirilgano`quvqo`llanma). Toshkent, «O`qituvchi», 1986.
8. Agnew.W.G. “Automotive Fuel Economy Improvement”, General Motors Research Publication GMR-3493
9. Cole D.E., Harbeck L.T. and Smith D.N. “Delphi Forecast and Analysis of the U.S. Automotive Industry in the 1980’S”, Othee for the study of Automotive Transportation and IndusttrialDevolopment Div. of the Institute of s’cience and tech (1991)
10. Coon C.W. and Wood C.D. Improvement of Automobile Fuel Economy, - SAE Paper 740969, october, 1984
11. Saunders J. SAE-A Truck Fuel Consumption Measurement Procedure: Tupe 1 Test. SAE Australasia. 1984, XI-XII.
12. Joshida E. Namura H., Hozaki H., etalJasoline Volatility Hot Weather Driveability of Japanese cars. Motor vehicle technology.
13. Dr-Ing. Wolf-Heinrich Hucho. Aerodynamik des Automobiles. 1987
14. Hucho W-H., Emmelmann, H-J. AerodynamischeFormoptimierung, einWegzurSteigerung der Wirtschaftlichkeit von Nutzfahzeugen.
15. Go’’tz, H.DieAerodynamik des Nutzfahzeuges – MassnahmenrurKroftstoffeinsporung. Reihe 12, 1987.